

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS IN REMOVABLE PROSTHETICS

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Abstract

Dental prostheses are an irritant to the tissues of the oral cavity, because they exert pressure in certain areas of the prosthetic bed. Complications can manifest as pain, burning, tingling, numbness, etc. The goal is to improve the method of preventing pain when using removable dentures, creating conditions for preventing pain and increasing the sensitivity threshold of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic field.

Keywords: orthopedic dentistry, pain syndrome, removable dentures, microneedle therapy.

Orthopedic dental treatment is a serious intervention in the human body. Negative emotions and pain are stress factors that negatively affect the functional state of the cardiovascular system of healthy people and especially patients with pathology of the circulatory organs [8]. Orthopedic dental treatment may be accompanied by pain of a different nature, impaired sensitivity and the appearance of various paresthesias (burning, itching, tingling, patience, etc.) [1;5]. Dental prostheses are an irritant to the tissues of the oral cavity, because they put excessive pressure on certain areas of the prosthetic bed. It is well known that a large number of patients using removable dentures cannot get used to them because of the occurrence of pain [2;3]. Removable dentures and the materials from which they are made damage the oral mucosa. Mechanical trauma occurs, accompanied by inflammatory reactions from the oral mucosa, allergic reactions, and increased atrophic processes [7]. At the same time, the attention of an orthopedic dentist is most often directed to the treatment of complications that have arisen after the imposition of a removable prosthesis, while their prevention is no less important [4;6]. The relevance of the issue lies in the fact that it is necessary to create such a prosthesis or such conditions for using it that prevent the development of secondary pathologies [9; 10].

Modern authors suggest the use of immunocorrective preparations Likopid and Imudon. They reduce complications from the oral mucosa of prosthetic wearers due to the ability to cause the creation of antibodies, thereby weakening inflammation and stimulating the human immune system in a natural way [11].

The disadvantage of this method of treatment is the inability to prevent inflammation before the use of dentures. Therefore, work in this direction is relevant.

Our study is based on the goal of improving the method of preventing pain syndrome, in which, by making changes to the special preparation for prosthetics and the means of preventing inflammatory phenomena, conditions are created to prevent pain syndrome

and increase the sensitivity threshold of the mucosa of the prosthetic field.

Materials and methods

The study involved 10 patients with complete removable dentures for the upper and lower jaws. Patients indicated poor fixation, pain when using prostheses.

The task is solved by using electropuncture diagnostics of the state of the tissues of the dentoalveolar system by the method of R. Voll, that is, the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the alveolar processes and palate is determined. After that, the auricular points of the earlobe zone are determined. Micro acupuncture is carried out by continuous exposure to a group of acupuncture points, the duration of exposure is 7 days. When using prolonged auricular microneedle therapy with needle-buttons, the sensitivity threshold of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic field will be increased to prevent pain (pain) during orthopedic treatment using removable prostheses. shell, tooth with its ligamentous apparatus and the corresponding fragment of the alveolar process of the jaw.

The results of electrical measurements of the points are entered into the examination card of patients according to the current standard energy ranges in electropuncture diagnostics: 50±1-65 UOP, 66-100 UOP, 48-0UOP (R. Voll, 1993). After determining pain points, auricular micro acupuncture. For patients using auriculotherapy for the first time, sessions should be performed in the supine position. Special needle-buttons are placed in the classical way on the auricular points of the ear. Compared to microneedles for cocoral points, they are smaller in size, and the needle shaft is perpendicular to the branches of the pen. Use the following points:

zone I - earlobe;

AD 1 I - the highest point of analgesia during tooth extraction;

AO 2 I - sky (point of the upper part of the mouth) cavities);

AO 3 I - floor of the mouth;

AO 4 I - language;

AO 5 I - upper jaw;

AD 6 I - lower jaw;

AD 7 I - the lower point of analgesia during tooth extraction.

Microneedle therapy is carried out in cycles, continuously affecting a group of acupuncture points. The duration of the cycle is 7 days, because needles with silver are used. Then take a break between cycles of 5 days. To achieve a significant clinical effect, as well as for auricular microneedle therapy. After each cycle, electropuncture diagnostics is carried out by the method of R. Voll. After lowering the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the alveolar processes and the palate in the most characteristic areas of pressure, prosthetics are carried out with removable dentures.

Patients underwent electropuncture diagnostics by R. Voll's method. In order to obtain comparative data, the most characteristic zones of pressure on the alveolar processes and the palate were determined in the area of 16, 14, 12, 22, 24, 26, 32, 34, 36, 42, 44, 46 teeth and on the vestibular and oral surfaces, along the crest alveolar process and in the area of the vestibular and oral. After electroacupuncture measurement, it was determined that the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the processes and the palate fluctuates on average within 69–74 SPV in the most characteristic pressure zones with removable dentures. In parallel, complete dentures were made for the upper and lower jaws. Prostheses are corrected and handed over on the day of the end of the course of auricular microneedle therapy.

Research results.

After the end of the 3rd cycle, electroacupuncture measurement determined that the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucosa of the alveolar processes and the palate in patients decreased on average to an interval of up to 54 to 58 SPV in the most characteristic zones of pressure with removable dentures. Control examinations were carried out after three days, a week and a month. Patients did not complain about pain when using removable dentures. Using electroacupuncture measurements, it was determined that the threshold of pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the alveolar processes and palate is at the normal level.

Conclusion

Therefore, the use of auricular microneedle therapy, carried out in cycles lasting 7 days with an interval of 5 days, reduces the pain sensitivity of the mucous membrane of the alveolar processes and the palate to the norm, which significantly shortens and facilitates the period of adaptation to complete removable dentures.

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